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Titel

Combined micromorphological, soil chemical and microbiological analyses of soils from St. Martha Cove and Brandy Bay, James Ross Island, Maritime Antarctica

Abstract

In the extreme environment of the Antarctic Peninsula Region, soil biological processes are primarily controlled by microbial communities, and thus microbiota may also determine soils chemical and physical properties in a landscape lacking higher plants at an average air temperature below 0°C.

The northern part of James Ross Island represents one of the biggest ice-free areas in the Antarctic Peninsula Region and offers the unique opportunity to study soil formation without the influence of vascular plants and burrowing animals.

We analysed micromorphological features, chemical and microbiological properties of soils from Brandy Bay (BB) and St. Martha Cove (SMC). Both sites are located at similar topographic positions (small plateaus at around 80m a.s.l.) and at similar substrates deriving from mostly fine-grained cretaceous sandstones and siltstones. The sites represent windward (BB) and leeward (SMC) conditions with respect to the mainly southwesterly winds. The climate is semi-arid polar-continental.

First results show that the different positions have effects on soil formation. Due to soluble salts from sea spray transported by wind, the electric conductivity differs between both sites from 39-61 $\mu\text{S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$, at the leeward site to values from 957 – 974 $\mu\text{S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ at the windward site. While the Fe_t/Fe_d ratio at SMC increases with depth (6.78–10.37) the ratio decreases at BB (6.54–5.05). The N content is quite stable with ca. 0.4 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ across both profiles. The C_t content increases with depth (7.89–10.17 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) and has 1 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ across the profile at SMC. The pH is similar at both sides ranging from 7.8 to 8.9.

Micromorphological analyses show that fissure microstructure is present from 0-10 cm at SMC. Additionally, moderately separated lenticular to banded microstructure occurs here from 30-60 cm. Subangular blocky to lenticular microstructure is present at Brandy Bay. The microstructure has a higher degree of separation at BB that can be caused by moister conditions at this site. Frequently occurring lenticular microstructure including cappings implicate freezing and thawing as dominant processes of soil formation at both sites.

Results on microbiology will be presented at the conference.